

<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2025.01.32>
<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:26A70364-0ADA-472B-A1AE-6A009E08B614>

● Description of *Aposthonia limushana* sp. nov. (Embioptera: Oligotomidae) from Hainan Province, China

Zhi-Teng CHEN^{1*} & Bo-Tao YAN²

¹School of Grain Science and Technology, Jiangsu University of Science and Technology, Zhenjiang 212004, Jiangsu Province, China;

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6331-8978>; 741208116@qq.com

²Institute of Tropical Agriculture and Forestry, Hainan University, Haikou 570228, Hainan Province, China;

<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-7795-445X>; 1478462770@qq.com

*Corresponding author

Abstract: *Aposthonia limushana* sp. nov. is described and illustrated based on male morphological characters from Hainan Province, China. This species is distinguished by a unique configuration of male terminalia, including an unmodified apically pointed left hemitergal process (10LP) and a finger-shaped right hemitergal process (10RP) with a rounded outer margin and truncate inner margin at its apex. This discovery elevates the number of documented *Aposthonia* species in China to three. A key to adult males of Chinese *Aposthonia* species is provided.

Keywords: Biodiversity, Hainan Island, new species, taxonomy, webspinner

● 中国海南省黎母山裸尾丝蚁（纺足目：等尾丝蚁科）一新种记述

陈志腾^{1*} & 晏博韬²

¹粮食学院，江苏科技大学，镇江 212004，江苏省，中国

²热带农林学院，海南大学，海口 570228，海南省，中国

*通讯作者

摘要：本文记述产自中国海南省的足丝蚁一新种——黎母山裸尾丝蚁 *Aposthonia limushana* sp. nov.。该物种雄性腹部末端具有独特构造，包括一未修饰、顶端尖锐的左半背板突起（10LP）和一指状的右半背板突起（10RP），其顶端外缘为圆形，内缘为截形。此新种的发现使中国已知的裸尾丝蚁属物种增至三种。本文提供了中国裸尾丝蚁属雄性成虫的鉴定检索表。

关键词：生物多样性，海南岛，新物种，分类学，足丝蚁

Citation: Chen Z-T & Yan B-T 2025: Description of *Aposthonia limushana* sp. nov. (Embioptera: Oligotomidae) from Hainan Province, China. *The Indochina Entomologist*, 1 (32): 311–318. [陈志腾 & 晏博韬 2025: 中国海南省黎母山裸尾丝蚁（纺足目：等尾丝蚁科）一新种记述. 中南半岛昆虫学家, 1 (32): 311–318.]
<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2025.01.32>

Accepted by Cheng-Bin WANG: 24.II.2025; published online: 25.II.2025

Copyright Zhi-Teng CHEN & Bo-Tao YAN. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CCBY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

● Introduction

The genus *Aposthonia* Krauss, 1911 (Embioptera: Oligotomidae) comprises 26 species distributed across the Oriental and Australian regions (Poolprasert *et al.* 2011a; Chen 2022). Taxonomic revisions of this genus have been comprehensively reviewed by Poolprasert *et al.* (2011a). Prior to this study, only two species were recorded from China: *Aposthonia borneensis* (Hagen, 1885) documented in Guangdong, Hainan, and Hong Kong (Ross 1978; Lu 1987, 1990), and *Aposthonia guizhouensis* Chen, 2022 from Guizhou Province (Chen 2022). Notably, a putative *Aposthonia* species reported from Hainan by Lu (1990) was later reclassified under *Eosembia* Ross, 2007 (Poolprasert *et al.* 2011b). Molecular studies by Chen *et al.* (2017) elucidated the mitochondrial genome of *A. borneensis*, while Ross (2007) hypothesized that numerous undescribed *Aposthonia* species likely persist in understudied regions of southwestern China.

This study describes *Aposthonia limushana* **sp. nov.**, collected from Limushan, Hainan Province, representing the third *Aposthonia* species recorded in China. Diagnostic morphological traits of the male terminalia unequivocally differentiate it from congeners. A key to Chinese *Aposthonia* males is included to facilitate future identifications.

● Material and methods

The holotype male was manually collected from a pine forest in Limushan, Hainan Province (coordinates: 19.175546°N, 109.799089°E) on 3 November 2023 and preserved in 75% ethanol. Morphological examinations were conducted using a SDPTOP SZM45 stereomicroscope. High-resolution images were captured with a Canon EOS 5DSR camera fitted with a Canon MP-E 65 mm 5X macro lens, post-processed in Adobe Photoshop (Beta). The holotype is deposited in the Insect Collection of Jiangsu University of Science and Technology (ICJUST), Jiangsu Province, China. Morphological terminology follows Ross (1948, 2007). Abbreviations: **MA** (anterior medial vein); **10L/R** (left/right hemitergite of abdominal segment 10); **10LP/RP** (left/right hemitergal process); **EP** (epiproct); **H** (hypandrium); **HP** (hypandrial process); **LPPT** (left paraproct); **LCB** (left cercus-basipodite); **LC1/2** (first/second segment of left cercus); **RC1/2** (first/second segment of right cercus).

● Taxonomy

Family Oligotomidae Enderlein, 1909

Genus *Aposthonia* Krauss, 1911

Aposthonia limushana **sp. nov.** 黎母山裸尾丝蚁

<https://zoobank.org/B3ACD571-7204-4BBD-9DDA-CC8A8978C9E6>

Figs. 1–5

Type material. Holotype: ♂ (ICJUST): **CHINA:** Hainan Province, Qiongzong Li and Miao Autonomous County, Limushan, Limu Temple scenic area, pine forest near entrance (Fig. 1), 19.175546°N, 109.799089°E, 3-XI-2023, Bo-Tao Yan.

Etymology. The specific epithet refers to the type locality, Limushan.

Description of holotype. *Size.* Body length (from anterior of maxillary palps to cercal apex) ca. 7.5 mm (Fig. 2).

Head. Head capsule pale brown, near 1.5 times longer than wide, with reticular pigmentation (Fig. 3A, B). Eyes large, sides behind eyes rounded, gradually converging posteriorly. Clypeus pale, near trapezoidal. Maxillary palpi brown, five-segmented; labial palpi brown and short, three-segmented. Submentum pale brown, subquadrate, anterior and posterior margins concave, lateral margins rounded. Antennae pale brown to brown, gradually darkened toward apical segments, at least 19-segmented.

FIGURE 1. *Aposthonia limushana* sp. nov., male holotype: **A** habitat forest in Limushan **B** stream (water source) near collecting site.

FIGURE 2. *Aposthonia limushana* sp. nov., male holotype: **A** habitus, dorsal view **B** habitus, ventral view. Scale bar = 1 mm.

Thorax. Prothorax brown, near trapezoidal, much shorter and narrower than head, with subequal length and width, surface with deep transverse and longitudinal grooves. Meso- and metathorax generally brown, width subequal to head. Wings pale brown (Fig. 2), with longitudinal pale stripes; MA unforked. Legs brown, articulations pale; hind basitarsus with single ventral papilla (Fig. 3C).

Abdomen. Abdomen brown, terminalia darker (Fig. 2). Hemitergites 10L and 10R subequal in size (Fig. 4). 10LP slender, hook-shaped, slightly curved outward, gradually tapered to pointed apex. 10RP longer and near 1.5 times wider than 10LP, thickness mostly uniform; apex subtriangular in dorsal view, outer margin rounded, inner margin truncate. EP weakly sclerotized, longitudinal, slender, near four times longer than wide, lateral margins slightly concave. H broad (Fig. 5), posterior margin truncate; right posterolateral margin deeply concave, left margin rounded. HP subtriangular, angles obtuse. LPPT small, sclerotized, hook-shaped in ventral view, gradually reduced in width toward apex; in dorsal view, LPPT reduced to thin, obliquely oriented sclerite with outwardly curved apex. LCB darkly sclerotized, subquadrate, fused to cercal base, with obtuse corners. LC1 medially dilated, without lobes; RC1 near cylindrical, mostly uniform in width.

Diagnosis. *Aposthonia limushana* sp. nov. is assigned to Oligotomidae based on the unforked MA, asymmetrical male terminalia, broad tergite 10 connection between hemitergites, and unfused LC2/LC1 (Ross 2007; Miller *et al.* 2012). Generic placement is confirmed by the single hind basitarsal papilla and absence of projected LCB (Ross 2007; Poolprasert *et al.* 2011a). The species is unambiguously distinguished from congeners by the combination of an apically unmodified 10LP and a finger-shaped 10RP whose apex has rounded outer margin and truncate inner margin (Ross 1978; Poolprasert *et al.* 2011a; Chen 2022). This discovery presents the third species of *Aposthonia* known from China and underscores the unexplored diversity of *Aposthonia* in tropical and subtropical regions of China.

FIGURE 3. *Aposthonia limushana* **sp. nov.**, male holotype: **A** head and thorax, dorsal view **B** head and thorax, ventral view **C** right hind leg, dorsal view. Scale bar = 0.5 mm. **pa** (papilla).

Key to adult males of *Aposthonia* species from China

- 1 10RP apex with distinct outer hook.....*A. borneensis*
- 10RP apex lacking outer hook.....**2**
- 2 10 LP apex with outer hook.....*A. guizhouensis*
- 10 LP apex unmodified, lacking outer hook.....*A. limushana* **sp. nov.**

FIGURE 4. *Aposthonia limushana* sp. nov., male holotype: terminalia, dorsal view. Scale bar = 0.1 mm. **10L/R** (left/right hemitergite of abdominal segment 10) **10LP/RP** (left/right hemitergal process) **EP** (epiproct) **LPPT** (left paraproct) **LC1/2** (first/second segment of left cercus) **RC1/2** (first/second segment of right cercus).

FIGURE 5. *Aposthonia limushana* sp. nov., male holotype: terminalia, ventral view. Scale bar = 0.1 mm. **10LP/RP** (left/right hemitergal process) **H** (hypandrium) **HP** (hypandrial process) **LPPT** (left paraproct) **LCB** (left cercus-basipodite) **LC1/2** (first/second segment of left cercus) **RC1/2** (first/second segment of right cercus).

● Acknowledgements

The authors thank the editor and reviewers for their insightful and constructive comments, which significantly enhanced the quality of this manuscript.

● References

- Chen Z-T 2022: *Aposthonia guizhouensis* sp. nov., a new webspinner of Oligotomidae (Insecta: Embioptera) from China. *Zootaxa*, 5213 (2): 190–198.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5213.2.7>
- Chen Z-T, Lü L, Lu M-X & Du Y-Z 2017: Comparative mitogenomic analysis of *Aposthonia borneensis* and *Aposthonia japonica* (Embioptera: Oligotomidae) reveals divergent evolution of webspinners. *Scientific Reports*, 7 (1): 1–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-09003-9>
- Enderlein G 1909: Die Klassifikation der Embiidinen, nebst morphologischen und physiologischen Bemerkungen, besonders über das Spinnen derselben. *Zoologischer Anzeiger*, 35: 166–191.
- Hagen HA 1885: Monograph of the Embidina. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 17: 141–230.
<https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent17141-8>
- Krauss HA 1911: Monographie der Embien. *Zoologica, Stuttgart*, 23: 1–78.
- Lu C-C 1987: Cold tolerance of *Aposthonia borneensis*. *Chinese Bulletin of Entomology*, 24 (5): 285–286. [卢川川 1987: 婆罗洲丝蚁的耐寒性. *昆虫知识*, 24 (5): 285–286.]
- Lu C-C 1990: A new species and a new record of Embiidina from Hainan Island (Embioptera: Oligotomidae). *Acta Zootaxonomica Sinica*, 15 (3): 323–326. [卢川川 1990: 海南蛛目昆虫一新种及一新纪录. *动物分类学报*, 15 (3): 323–326.]
- Miller KB, Hayashi C, Whiting MF, Svenson GJ & Edgerly JS 2012: The phylogeny and classification of Embioptera (Insecta). *Systematic Entomology*, 37 (3): 550–570.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3113.2012.00628.x>
- Poolprasert P, Sitthicharoenchai D, Butcher BA & Lekprayoon C 2011a: *Aposthonia* Krauss, 1911 (Embioptera: Oligotomidae) from Thailand, with description of a new species. *Zootaxa*, 2937 (1): 37–48.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.2937.1.3>
- Poolprasert P, Sitthicharoenchai D, Lekprayoon C & Butcher BA 2011b: Two remarkable new species of webspinners in the genus *Eosembia* Ross, 2007 (Embioptera: Oligotomidae) from Thailand. *Zootaxa*, 2967 (1): 1–11.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.2967.1.1>
- Ross ES 1948: The Embioptera of New Guinea. *Pan-Pacific Entomologist*, 24: 97–116.
- Ross ES 1978: The Embiidina of China. *Memoirs of the Hong Kong Natural History Society*, 13: 1–8.
- Ross ES 2007: The Embiidina of Eastern Asia, Part I. *Proceedings of the California Academy of Sciences*, 58: 575–600.

● Additional information

Author contributions: Conceptualization, Resources, Writing–review and editing: B-T Yan. Visualization, Writing–original draft: Z-T Chen.

Conflict of interest: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Data availability: All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

Ethical statement: No ethical statement was reported.

Funding: This study was self-funded by the authors.

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of *ICE* and/or the editor(s). *ICE* and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.